

1 RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION ACTIVITIES

Skills and competence	Examples of a qualitative description	Examples of a quantitative description
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS AND OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS		
Scientific publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key scientific publications • Role in producing the publication • Most important pursued or achieved new openings in research • Scientific, societal and/or practical impact of the publications • Open access of publications, early sharing (preprints) and preregistration of the research • Novelty, originality and risk-taking • Multi-, trans- and interdisciplinarity • Significance of interdisciplinarity in the activities and achievements of the group or project 	Number of publications per publication type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-reviewed scientific articles • Non-refereed scientific writings • Scientific books (monographs) • Number of publications in different languages and number of translations • Number of publications produced in international collaboration or in collaboration with companies • Indicators based on publication metrics, such as number of publications and citations received by them, attention received by publications in social media and researcher networks
Publications intended for the professional community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and practical significance of the publications • Open access • Target group, language versions and formats of the publications • Peer review of the publications 	Number of publications per publication type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article in a professional journal, blog post • Article in a professional edited book • Article in professional conference proceedings • Published development or research report or study • Professional book • Edited professional volume; editorial work for a professional journal, edited book or conference proceedings, or for a scientific journal, edited book or conference proceedings • Development and innovation publications
Guides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the guides • Target group, language versions and formats of the guides • Open access 	Number of publications per publication type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional book, textbook or guidebook
Policy recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption and implementation of the recommendations • Impacts on the policies pursued • Target group of the recommendations and policy level • Language versions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of policy recommendations

<i>Skills and competence</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
Patents and inventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Merits related to development and innovation • Patents granted and their context and significance • Industrial or commercial utilisation of inventions and patents, such as start-up company, spin-off company 	Number of publications per publication type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent applications and granted patents • Invention disclosures
Popular publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the publications • Significance of the publications in promoting the researcher's own objectives for societal interaction • Target audience • Open access 	Number of publications per publication type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article in a journal • Article in an edited volume • Blog post • Monograph • Editorial work for a special issue of a popular journal, edited book or conference proceedings
Audiovisual publications and ICT applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and practical significance • Target group • Publication platforms and channels • Open access • Role in the development work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of works produced per type, such as podcasts, videos, mobile applications • Audiovisual publication • ICT application • Downloads

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION MERITS

Patents and inventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Merits related to development and innovation • Patents granted and their context and significance • Industrial or commercial utilisation of inventions and patents, such as start-up company, spin-off company 	Number of publications per publication type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent applications and granted patents • Invention disclosures
Combining research-based knowledge and practical work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the work and practical skills accumulated, such as clinical work or similar 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of work experience
RDI outputs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the outputs and services, own role in the activities • Produced operating models, concepts, tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of outputs, services and similar

Skills and competence	Examples of a qualitative description	Examples of a quantitative description
RESEARCH DATA, METHODS AND TOOLS		
Research materials and research data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Published and open research data and metadata • Role in producing the research materials or data • National, international and discipline-specific significance of the materials and data • Research data transferred to long-term storage • Application of the FAIR principles • Reproducibility, replicability, reusability of the research data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of published and open research materials and data and their metadata • Number of publications based on the materials or data • Downloads
Conference abstracts and posters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific, professional or popular conference at which the abstract or poster has been presented • Significance of the conference for researcher’s research and discipline • Societal impact of the conference • Open access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of abstracts and posters
Research methods, tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development, significance, open access and use of research methods • Methodological and collegial support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of published research methods • Citations
Programs, software, source codes, hardware, algorithms, simulations and geographic information developed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application areas • Open access to and reproducibility of programs, software, source codes, hardware, algorithms and workflows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of programs, pieces of software, open-source codes, hardware or algorithms • Number of research publications using the programs, software, source codes, hardware, algorithms, simulations and geographic information • Downloads • Citations
Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context, operation and significance of the infrastructure • Role in building, developing and maintaining the infrastructure • Open access 	
ARTISTIC ACTIVITIES		
Public artistic and design activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the artistic activity, for example public art institutions (institutional theatres, museums), independent scene, private galleries, community art, national and international activities • Role in the artistic activities • Acting as curator of exhibitions • Reception of artworks/performances, audience feedback and reviews • Research or writing based on artistic practice • Artistic works selected by juries • Societal impact of artistic work 	<p>Number of publications and outputs per publication type:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separate publication • Public artistic part-implementation • Artistic part of non-artistic publication • For example, concert, lecture-recital, curated art exhibition, extensive composition, leading role in an opera or play

<i>Skills and competence</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
PROJECTS, CONSORTIA AND FUNDING		
Applying for and receiving research, development and innovation funding; infrastructure funding; or funding for artistic activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the funding applied for or received • Role in applying for funding • Expert reviews of the application or project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding granted
Research, development and innovation projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the projects • Contribution to and role in project implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of projects
Activities in collaborative, or RDI consortia or organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the collaborative consortium • Contents of outputs and services • Role in the work of the consortium • Description of the activities of consortia that apply for research funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of outputs, services, events or similar produced by the consortium • Funding granted to the consortium
CONFERENCES AND EVENTS		
Invited lectures and presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic and target group of the invited lecture or presentation • Context and significance of the invited lecture or presentation • Inviting party 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of invited lectures
Participation in conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the conference • Role at the conference, such as invited speaker, panellist, presentation, poster 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of instances of participation in conferences • Funding granted for participation in conferences
Organising conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the conferences • Role in organising the conferences • National and international conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding granted for organising conferences
Organising scientific, artistic and professional events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the events • Role in organising the events • National and international events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding granted for organising events

Skills and competence	Examples of a qualitative description	Examples of a quantitative description
RESEARCH INTEGRITY, RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND OPEN SCIENCE		
Proficiency in and promotion of research integrity and good research practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familiarity with up-to-date practices of research integrity as well as ethical and accurate selection and use of research methods in general and in researcher’s discipline • Acting as research integrity adviser • Teaching courses related to research integrity and ethics or developing course materials • Membership in research integrity committees and working groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length and scope of teaching experience or other relevant experience related to research integrity • Length of experience as research integrity adviser • Number of research outputs related to research integrity
Management of research permit applications and data protection processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of research permit applications and data protection processes • Role in applying for research permits or in ethical reviews 	
Data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data management competence, such as knowledge of the FAIR principles • Competence in research integrity, responsible research practices and good scientific practice • Role in data management, such as acting as a data management support person (data steward, data agent) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of experience in data support
Promotion of open science and research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact and use of open publications, preprint versions, machine-readable data, research and laboratory notebooks, analysis code, methods or educational resources • Compliance with the FAIR principles in publishing and making research outputs openly accessible • Knowledge of and compliance with the CARE principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of open research outputs • Funding granted and projects carried out for the promotion of open science and research
RESEARCH SUPERVISION AND EVALUATION		
Acting as a dissertation supervisor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disciplines and subject areas of the supervised dissertations • Supervisory role, such as principal supervisor, member of a follow-up group • Ability to provide constructive criticism and feedback • Introduction into the research processes, such as publication processes, applying for funding • Supervision principles and assessment of one’s development as a supervisor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of supervised doctoral dissertations • Ongoing doctoral supervisions
Acting as a preliminary examiner of dissertation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disciplines and subject areas of the dissertations examined • Ability to provide constructive criticism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of doctoral dissertations examined

<i>Skills and competence</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
Acting as an opponent for doctoral dissertations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disciplines and subject areas of the public defences at which one has served as opponent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of instances of acting as an opponent
Memberships in dissertation committees or boards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of committees and boards • Role in the activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of memberships in dissertation committees or boards
COLLABORATION AND RECOGNITIONS		
Participation in cross-, inter- or multidisciplinary teams and projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the team or project • Role in the team or project 	
National and international collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context, significance and own role in mobility, such as research visits, exchange studies, short intensive periods • Possible barriers to mobility periods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and duration of mobility periods
Awards and accolades received for scientific, artistic, research or professional merits or on the basis of the academic career	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the award or accolade, such as internal to the organisation, national, international • Merits mentioned in the award justifications • Artistically awarded works on a national or international level • Awarding body • For example, State Award for Public Information, National Open Science and Research Awards • State honours 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of awards and accolades
<p>You may also consider examining the following skills and competencies in this section: <i>experience of leading a research or artistic group, project experience, application of research in different sectors, integration of research or teaching and RD&I activities, entrepreneurship and innovation activities, commercialisation of research, collaboration with companies, editorial work, peer review of scientific manuscripts, peer review of funding applications, acting as an expert evaluator in recruitment processes.</i></p>		

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TEACHING AND PEDAGOGY		
Teaching experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of teaching experience • Role as a teacher, such as responsible teacher or teaching assistant • Courses planned and implemented independently or as team work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of teaching experience • Number and scope of courses taught, number of students
Teaching skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student-centred learning • Research-based teaching • Mastery of various teaching methods • Overall assessment of teaching skills, teaching demonstration • Feedback from students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical course feedback
Pedagogical competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedagogical education, development of pedagogical skills and other demonstrated pedagogical competence, subject-didactic competence • Pedagogical reflection, pedagogical theory-in-practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount and scope of pedagogical or other relevant studies, such as study credits
International or multilingual teaching experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of international teaching experience, such as in different countries, educational institutions, levels of education and disciplines • International teaching visits • Languages of instruction used 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and scope of teaching visits and courses taught in foreign languages, such as study credits
Integration of education and RDI activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities in RDI learning environments, such as digital learning environments, company visits, workshops • Engaging students in projects • Building networks and partnerships • Representativeness of different sectors among collaboration partners • International partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of projects and funding granted for them • Number of collaboration partners
Accolades awarded for teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significance of the award or accolade, such as organisation-specific or national • Merits mentioned in the award justifications • Awarding body • For example, Teacher of the Year awards of individual organisations, Open Education Awards granted by the National Open Science and Research Coordination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of accolades awarded for teaching

Skills and competence	Examples of a qualitative description	Examples of a quantitative description
SUPERVISORY TASKS		
Supervision of bachelor's and master's degree students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of supervision experience, such as theses supervised at different degree levels • Supervisory role • Diversity of research fields and research topics, multidisciplinary • Supervision of thesis seminars and courses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of theses supervised
Mentoring and supervision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of mentoring or supervision of students, doctoral researchers or postdoctoral researchers • Principles of mentoring and supervision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of persons mentored or supervised
Supervision of work placements and cooperation with working life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in developing work placement models • Building work placement partnerships and working life networks • Acting as work placement supervisor • Supporting career planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of supervised students undertaking a work placement
DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHING AND LEARNING		
Development and production of educational resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity and timeliness of the educational resources • Educational resources for different levels of education and target groups • Utilisation of feedback or evaluations received about the educational resources in development • Formats of the educational resources • Materials for entrance examinations • Openness, accessibility and compliance with the FAIR principles of learning and educational resources • Adoption of the educational resources created across other courses • Peer-reviewed educational resources, peer review of educational resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of educational resources produced • Print run and number of editions of books • Number of downloads of educational resources
Development of learning methods and tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in working groups related to the development of teaching • Collaborative development of teaching methods • Participation in teaching development projects • Practices developed and their significance for learning and teaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of relevant studies, such as scope of courses or number of study credits • Number of publications on applied teaching methods and the experiences gained from them

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Development of teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives and significance of the development work • Research-based development of teaching • Role in working groups or projects related to teaching development • Practices and methods developed • Sharing teaching practices related to, for example, planning, implementation or assessment of teaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of publications and reports related to teaching • Number of keynote lectures or presentations related to teaching development • Number of projects piloting teaching methods
Funding applied for and granted for the development of teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the funding applied for or granted • Objectives or achievements of the project • Role in applying for funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding granted
ADMINISTRATIVE AND SPECIAL TASKS IN TEACHING		
Training activities outside the higher education and research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives and significance of the training activities • Target groups of the training activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of training modules such as lectures and courses • Number of participants
Work related to entrance examinations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities in entrance examination boards • Preparation and assessment of entrance examinations 	
Management roles related to teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership of a degree or an education programme • Membership in a management group related to education or teaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of experience in management roles related to teaching

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SCIENCE COMMUNICATION		
Popularisation of research, development and innovation activities and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Popularisation in different forums, for different audiences and in different formats, such as blog posts, exhibitions, interviews, journal articles, non-fiction books or public lectures • Grants and awards for non-fiction literature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of sales and loans of non-fiction books • Number of interviews, writings or public lectures • Visitor numbers of exhibitions or events
Multilingual science communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content production and communication in different languages or multilingually • Development of scientific terminology in different languages • Translations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of publications in different languages and number of translations • Language distribution of publications
Acting as an expert in the media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context, objectives and significance of the activities • Active participation in discussions related to researcher's areas of expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figures describing researcher's activity and engagement (such as mentions, references, interactions on social media, etc.)
Activities on social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context, objectives and significance of the activities • Active participation in discussions related to researcher's areas of expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figures describing researcher's activity and engagement (such as mentions, references, interactions on social media, etc.)
Positions of trust and expert roles outside the research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the positions • Description of positions of trust, expert roles or commissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of positions
Interaction with decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives and significance of the interaction • Interaction with relevant stakeholders and networks • Science sparring • Pursued or proven impact of the interaction on decision-making • Participation in scientific advisory bodies and science panels • Collaboration with ministries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy citations • Number of publications (such as policy briefs) targeted at decision-makers • Number of statements and committee hearings
Citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role in projects or events involving citizen science or collaborative research • Engagement of citizens • Crowdsourced science, participatory monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizen science and similar projects, events or occasions • Number of participants

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APPLIED RESEARCH		
Activities in different sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities and experience in different sectors, such as higher education, public administration, the private sector or organisations • Context and significance of the activities • Networks • Collaboration with different stakeholders in research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of co-authored publications with stakeholders • Length of work experience in different sectors • Number of joint projects • Guest lectures in education
Applying research in different sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context of the application of research in different sectors, such as public administration, the private sector or the third sector • Significance of applying research • The researcher's role in developing the application 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • References in policy citations or other relevant publications
Research-based teaching or training outside the higher education and research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the teaching or training • Science education projects • Visits to educational institutions or science events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of students or participants • Scope and duration of teaching • Number of training modules
Integration of research or education and RDI activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities in RDI learning environments, such as digital learning environments, company visits, workshops • Engaging students in projects • Building networks and partnerships • Representativeness of different sectors among collaboration partners • International partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of projects and funding granted for them • Number of collaboration partners
Entrepreneurship and innovation activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of entrepreneurship and innovation activities • Start-up business activities • Spin-off business activities • Participation in business incubator activities • Development of services, products, processes and practices based on research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding granted
Commercialisation of research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of utilising patents and inventions • Context and significance of development and innovation publications, such as emerging and developing technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of innovations that ended up in industrial production • Number of patents and inventions
UN Sustainable Development Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significance of work or research in promoting the Sustainable Development Goals, such as tools or actions for promoting the SDGs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of publications linked to the UN SDGs in different databases or services

<i>Skills and competence</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
COLLABORATION		
Collaboration with businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives, context and significance of collaboration and partnerships • Business networks • Role in collaborations and networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of joint projects • Guest lectures in education • Research or development funding received from businesses • Number of commissioned research
Science–art collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives, context and significance of the collaborations • Role in collaboration projects, exhibitions, performances or projects • Creativity and originality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of collaboration projects or outputs created through them • Number of visitors
Development cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives, context and significance of the development cooperation projects • Role in the activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of development cooperation projects
<p><i>You may also consider examining the following aspects in this section: guides, policy recommendations, patents and inventions.</i></p>		

<i>Skills and competence</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
EVALUATION AND EDITORIAL WORK		
Editorial work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the editorial work • Role in scientific, professional or popular editorial work, such as membership of editorial boards • Scope of editorial responsibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of editorial boards • Length of editorial experience
Peer review of scientific manuscripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the peer review work • Making peer review statements openly accessible • Certificates granted by publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of peer reviewed manuscripts and other review assignments
Acting as an expert evaluator in filling open positions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the evaluation work • Description of the activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of expert or evaluation assignments
Peer review of funding applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of reviewed funding applications • Role in reviewing the applications • Making peer review statements openly accessible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of review assignments
POSITIONS OF TRUST AND COMMUNITY TASKS		
Participation in expert, evaluation and steering groups, regulatory monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of expert tasks • Role and responsibilities in the group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of memberships and positions of trust • Duration of the activities
Positions in the administration or working groups of higher education institutions and research organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the positions • Role in administrative work and working groups • Outputs produced as a result of the activities as well as their adoption and/or implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of working groups • Number of new operating models, policies etc. • Duration of the work
National and international positions of trust in science, art and research administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the positions of trust • Role in the positions of trust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of positions

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Participation in scientific and artistic associations and learned societies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the association or society • Role in the association or society, such as chair, secretary, treasurer • Contributions to the activities of the association or society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of associations or societies • Duration of the activities
Participation in professional advocacy organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributions to and role in the activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the activities
Activities in research, development and innovation networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the network • Role in the network's activities, such as acting as chair or member of the board • Contribution to the network's activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of networks • Duration of the activities
Participation in the activities of open science communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role and activities in communities such as open science communities, peer review communities, reproducibility networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the activities
MANAGEMENT AND LEADERSHIP		
Experience in leading a research group or artistic group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the research or artistic group • Description of the leadership style • Diversity and interdisciplinarity of the research group or artistic group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of experience
Project experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significance and context of the project • Researcher's role in different phases of the project • Description of the scope of the project, such as national or international, or cross-sectoral • Inter- and multidisciplinary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of projects • Funding granted for the projects
Leadership experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the leadership experience, such as acting as dean or member of the faculty administration • Context and significance of leadership experience, such as private and public sector, third sector, publishing sector • Role in the management activities • Financial management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of leadership experience

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Administrative work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and significance of the work • Role in the administrative work, such as the preparation of projects and recruitments • Project expertise in different phases of the project, such as in project administration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of experience
Experience in supervisory work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational role • Supporting wellbeing at work • Developing the work culture • Developing supervisory skills • Leading international teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of supervisory experience • Number of subordinates
Leadership skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership style, values, goals and innovations • Utilisation of feedback in developing leadership • Courses and training related to leadership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and scope of relevant studies, courses and training modules
Promotion of social responsibility, e.g. equality, diversity and non-discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role in promoting equality, diversity and non-discrimination • Promotion of wellbeing at work 	

<i>Information</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
Self-management and organisation of work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation and scheduling of researcher's work and prioritisation of responsibilities • Ability to work under pressure • Ability to work in challenging and uncertain situations • Ability to identify room for improvement and do career planning • Efficient use of resources • Maintaining and developing personal competence, lifelong learning 	
Cognitive skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abstract, critical and analytical thinking • Strategic thinking and ability to anticipate things • Problem-solving skills • Creativity 	
Communication and interaction skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General communication skills • Negotiation skills • Mediation skills and conflict resolution • Networking skills • Social media skills • Ability to inspire and motivate others • Ability to give and receive constructive feedback 	
Cooperation skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social skills • Ability to participate in collaboration projects as well as various teams and groups • Co-creation skills • Collegiality and participation in improving wellbeing in the work community • Ability to build supervisory relationships 	

<i>Information</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
Researcher identifiers	<p>Researcher identifier and link, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORCID, Research.fi, profile in a research information system 	
Degrees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major, degree programme, provider and date of completion of the degree • What essential competence the degree demonstrates • Grades and the strengths and competencies highlighted in statements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of degrees completed • Number of study credits completed
Titles of docent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of issue of the title of docent, the associated discipline and university • Strengths and competencies highlighted in statements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of titles of docent
Continuing education and other training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name, scope and provider of the education programme as well as its significance for the assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the education programme or the number of study credits completed
Vocational qualifications or professional certification, accredited competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name, scope and provider of the education programme as well as its significance for the assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the education programme or the number of study credits completed
Employment relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start and end date of the employment relationships and secondary occupation • Current job title • Employer and place of work • Stage of career, such as the stage of academic career in accordance with the four-stage (I–IV) research career model, adapted where necessary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the employment relationships
Grant periods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose and objective of grant-funded work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the grant periods
Leaves of absence during career	<p>Optional verbal description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family leaves, • Military service • Non-military service • Other leave of absence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the leaves of absence

<i>Information</i>	<i>Examples of a qualitative description</i>	<i>Examples of a quantitative description</i>
Language proficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First language • Proficiency level reached in other languages in accordance with CEFR and issue date of the certificate • Personal assessment of proficiency 	
IT skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various software applications • Programming and coding skills • Artificial intelligence • Information security skills • Drawing, layout, image and video editing software • Statistical software • IT skills required by researcher's discipline and relevant to work tasks 	